

ANALYSIS OF THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS RESULTING FROM THE AGRICULTURAL DYNAMISM IN THE STATE OF OUED SOUF

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Abstract

In recent years, the province of Oued Souf has witnessed an agricultural dynamism, which resulted in an expansion of the exploited agricultural lands, and a great diversity in agricultural crops. This is attributable to the Saharan farmer and his ability to adapt to the harsh conditions that characterize the Oued Souf region. However, this dynamism witnessed by the province was accompanied by many environmental problems, which we attempt to highlight through a field study carried out in the province of Oued Souf within the framework of the research project of an economic and social nature **New Agricultural Production Systems in Dry Areas: What Sustainability Case of the region of Oued Souf.** " at the Scientific and Technical Research Center for Arid Regions CRSTRA. The sample of the study included 120 female agricultural investors who were randomly selected and distributed among five municipalities as they rank first in terms of national production, and we aim through this study to highlight the most important environmental problems to avoid them in the future in order to achieve environmental sustainability.

Keywords: Saharan Agriculture, Environmental Risks, Sustainable Development.

1. INTRODUCTION

The first subtitle opens with an introduction that presents the specific problem under study and describes the research strategy. The first Agriculture in Algeria is one of the most important strategic sectors, aiming at achieving food security and contributing to the diversification of the national economy. The state has given it great attention in recent years, through the adoption of a number of measures and programs to promote it, especially in the Saharan areas, because of the unique economic and natural characteristics of these areas, which make them capable of driving economic growth. The Saharan agriculture in Algeria has witnessed a quantum leap in recent years, especially in the area of Oued Souf, which has experienced a major transformation in this sector. The previous agricultural system used to be known as 'al-But', but the latter experienced a crisis in the late 1980s due to the problem of rising water levels that submerged palm seedlings. This prompted residents, especially farmers, to consider moving to field agriculture and to prepare a new agricultural system based on different mechanisms and methods. This importance is not limited to the increase in the exploited area estimated at 100,000 hectares, but extends to the amount of plant production that is close to 20 million quintals, thus taking the national lead and achieving an estimated production value of more than 191 billion Dinar, with a growth rate of more than 7.47%, contributing by 6.4% to GDP. In addition, it ranks second in both industrial crops - peanuts, tobacco, and dates.

The sector also has a significant social impact with an estimated employment of more than 130,000 jobs, which covers 45% of the province's total labor force (Directorate of agricultural services, 2018, p. 01). Although the province of Oued Souf has achieved a great dynamism in Saharan farming, this dynamism has been accompanied by numerous environmental issues related to agricultural land, water resources and energy sources.

Based on this we posed the following main question:

The key question:

What were the most important adverse environmental impacts associated with agricultural dynamism in Oued Souf province?

Sub-questions:

To answer the main question, we ask the following sub-questions:

- What are the most important agricultural resources available in Oued Souf?
- What are the most important environmental impacts of agricultural dynamism in Oued Souf on agricultural land, water resources and energy sources?
- What are the most important solutions to reduce environmental risks to achieve sustainable development in Oued Souf?

Study goals:

Based on the main question and the sub-questions raised, the objectives of the study were as follows:

- To observe the agricultural dynamics of Oued Souf province by monitoring its most important components;
- Highlight the most important environmental problems caused by the development of agricultural dynamism in the province;
- Provide solutions and suggestions to avoid environmental problems to make agriculture in the province more sustainable while achieving food security.

Study Approach

In order to complete the study and answer the central question posed by the problems and the sub-questions, we adopted the descriptive method, which is appropriate in providing the data, information and facts on the subject of the research.

Data Collection and Analysis Tool:

We used an interview form to collect information, and created a pilot form in the first phase, which was then modified and finalized. It consisted of three main components: the first comprised general information about the farmer, the second, information regarding the investor, and the third covered sustainability indicators in their three dimensions: environmental, economic and social.

In data analysis, we used SPSS in data processing, as well as ARC GIS mapping and study positioning after we determined the coordinates using a GPS device.

Sample and Search Community:

The field survey included 120 specimens distributed over five municipalities of Wadi Souf (Hassi Khalifa, Trefaoui, Ouarmas, Regueb, Tagzot), which rank first in terms of production, particularly for potato production, at 70% of the general production of the Souf (see Supplement No. 02). The samples were randomly selected, and the field study took 27 days, 5 days to collect data from various agricultural actors, and then 22 days (2 × 11 days) to interview farmers on their farms.

2. THE REALITY OF THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR IN THE OUEDSOUF

Those who follow the situation of the agricultural sector in the Souf will realize the great attention paid by the state to this sector, given the great agricultural dynamic witnessed in the region, through the development of the agricultural area of crops and the development of the volume and diversity of production. (Saifi, 2021, p. 431)

2.1 Location:

The OuedSouf is a known Algerian province consisting of the two parts: the OuedSouf and Oued Rig, which are different in some customs and traditions, and in the nature of their land, and at the time in their construction. The valley is located in the northeast of the Algerian south. (Mani, 2014, p. 07)

In the greater North-East Irq, bordered to the North by Khenchela, to the Northeast by Tebessa, and to the North Westby Djelfa. The South and the West are bordered by the province of Ouargla. (Monography , 2015)

Fig 1: Study area

Source: Tarek Mokhnane.

2.2 Province Agricultural Sector Capacity:

The OuedSouf province is full of resources and potential that have made it a pioneer in the production of many agricultural products at the national level, despite its dry desert climate. We will try to present the most important of these factors:

- Population:

The total population for 2020 is estimated at 820,000, and the total labor force is 292,500, of which 130,800 are permanent workers, 80,700 are in the agricultural sector(Directorate of agricultural services, 2018, p. 01).

- Land areas and agricultural investments:

The total area of the OuedSouf is 4,458,680 hectares, of which 1,768,900 are for the total agricultural area, or 39.7%, of which 100,000 are for farming, or 5.7%, and the rest is estimated at 92,000 hectares, or 92%, and 1,410,000 hectares, or 79.7%. The amount of unproductive land destined for investment in agriculture was estimated at 258,000 hectares (14.6%). The total number of female investors is about 44,700 (Directorate of agricultural services, 2018, p. 02).

- Agricultural irrigation:

Irrigation plays an increasingly fundamental role in agricultural production, and hence national production, especially in arid and semi-arid regions, is one of the main pillars for ensuring the sustainability of agriculture in them.(Fallah & Bagat, 2020, p. 37). In OuedSouf, we will distinguish between the irrigation systems shown in the following table:

Table 1: Irrigation Systems in the EL-Oued Souf

submersion irrigation system	Pivotirrigation system	local irrigation system	Elghout	Percentage of water economy systems
30 377	33 851	26 195	1 577	92 000
33	36.8	28.5	1.7	67%

Source : DSA El-Oued Souf, 2020.

- Sector Framing:

The Agricultural Interests Directorate of the Valley was established in accordance with Executive Decree No. 90-195 of 23/06/1990, which sets out the rules for the organization and operation of the agricultural interests in the province. The latter consists of 5 (05) departments and 10 offices, in addition to 9 sub-sections in each section containing 2 offices. (Directorate of agricultural services, 2018, p. 02)

All of these departments and departments frame an estimated 247 tires and workers, divided as follows:

Table 2: Farmers in the agricultural sector

Engineers	veterinary	Technicians	Administrators	Professional workers
64	28	55	41	59

Source : DSA El-Oued Souf, 2020.

- Agricultural production in the OuedSouf:

Although the desert climate of the province is difficult, it was not an obstacle to the development and diversification of agricultural production in both plant and animal species.

• **Plant production:**

Agricultural production in the **OuedSouf** has grown considerably thanks to policies based on agricultural development and reclamation programs that have led to the emergence of previously unknown products in the region such as peanuts, grains, olives and potatoes. The crops have also diversified, altered and increased each other's area and production, as shown in the following table:

Table 3: Evolution of plant production unit (area: hectare, production, and quintal)

Years		crops					
		Dates	Cereal	fodder	Peanut	Potato	Tomato
2012	Space	26057	4731	2362	500	30200	845
	Output	2022870	121203	334292	6580	11176000	186127
2013	Space	36317	5500	1836	564	35000	1088
	Output	2137520	215820	262530	7340	11725000	543000
2014	Space	36335	8500	1925	570	33000	1228
	Output	2312000	317220	286000	14250	10890000	611000
2015	Space	36680	12000	2230	650	33000	2063
	Output	2474000	488000	331500	15860	10890000	1023000
2016	Space	37070	12000	2992	1670	34000	2520
	Output	2533100	528800	479020	50400	11180000	1785000
2017	Space	37440	14000	2654	2,300	35000	3070
	Output	2624400	570000	391200	83,000	11530000	2170000
2018	Space	37750	12612	2900	3000	36200	3130
	Output	2731200	302880	406800	97470	11360000	2163100
2019	Space	38147	10840	3710	4000	37000	3397
	Output	2752100	302440	493334	104850	12140000	2398000

Source : DSA El-Oued Souf, 2020

From the previous table which shows the development of food crop production, we notice that the province, despite its reputation for producing dates, which has witnessed a continuous increase in both production volume and cultivated area. The volume of production has doubled from 2312,000 quintals in 2014 to 2752,100 quintals in 2019, but it has seen the production of many field crops, making it one of the most important agricultural poles at the national level. It has led the production of potatoes, which is known to have developed in terms of area and volume of production. It estimated the largest area planted at the state in 2019, at 3010 hectares, and estimated the production value of 10 hectares in addition to many other field crops, such as peanuts, grains and tomatoes. This is what requires a fast-track approach to investment in transformation, packaging and export.

• **Animal production:**

Livestock is an integral part and supplement of agriculture in desert areas, and has always been associated with water resources like other sectors (Najah, Not mentioned, p. 80). The livestock production in the Wadi Souf province has been continuously increasing in recent years as a result of the government's policy of allocating substantial funding to farmers to increase their livestock and livestock products, as shown in the following table.

Table 4: The Zoological Census in the OuedSouf

Types	Sheep	Cows	Goat	Camels
2012	508000	3250	496000	34000
2013	538000	3500	526000	37000
2014	550000	16000	532000	38000
2015	560000	16500	540000	40000
2016	635000	22300	542000	42000
2017	716500	24415	498500	45000
2018	732000	26000	496000	55000

Source: DSA El-Oued Souf, 2020

From the table above, we note that the livestock production in the province has witnessed continuous increase in recent years, especially in sheep, cattle and camel breeding, with some fluctuations in goat breeding, the largest number of which was in 2016 with a total of 542,000 head. This increase in livestock volume in the province is due to the policies adopted by the state in this field, and by the allocation of large funds to support farmers, in addition to the increasing tendency to invest by the Sufi farmers in this field.

- **Animal products:**

Animal products in the OuedSouf have been on the upward trend in recent years, especially in the production of red and white meat, with some fluctuations in milk production especially during 2018 and 2019, as can be seen from the table below:

Table 5: Animal products

Types	Red meat	White meat	Milk(m ³)Litre
2012	105624	5759	31600
2013	109940	15438	31700
2014	123000	20000	32500
2015	127655	21570	32800
2016	148780	38815	33800
2017	149000	54700	35500
2018	152600	63188	33400
2019	159000	64890	32550

Source : DSA El-Oued Souf, 2020

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The environmental risks of an agricultural dynamism in Oued Souf:

In recent years, the province of Oued Souf has witnessed an agricultural boom, resulting in an expansion of exploited farmland and a large variety of crops. However, this dynamism has been accompanied by many environmental problems, which we will attempt to shed light on in order to achieve greater environmental sustainability in this province.

3.1 Waste and Leftover Agricultural Investments:

- Agricultural product harvesting waste:

Much of OuedSouf's farmland is being left behind after agricultural land has been cleared for recultivation, piling up next to farms (see photo 01) or being carried away by wind. This has negative environmental implications:

- Distortion of Environmental;
- Many diseases have been caused by inorganic fertilizers.

Photo 1: Waste from harvesting agricultural produce

Source: Our Field study

- Pesticide residue/waste (plastic bottles)

As confirmed by the results of the field study, most agricultural farms in El Oued province, like most agricultural farms nationwide, lack appropriate storage for pesticides and fertilizers used in agriculture. Through figure (02), we notice that 96.67% of the farms do not have places to store pesticides and fertilizers used in agriculture according to safety standard

Fig 2: Pesticides and fertilizer storage areas

Source: Our Field study

Random dumping of pesticide residues and fertilizers in agricultural farms (see pictures 02) has a negative impact on the environment, as these residues are not biodegradable in the short term and therefore are more harmful to humans and soil.

Photo 2: Pesticide residue and residue (plastic bottles)

Source: Our Field study

- Pivot irrigation waste

Pivot irrigation is one of the most common irrigation systems in the Oued Souf, a system first used in California, and then introduced to Algeria in 1995 by American companies investing in Adrar and Ouargla. The Sufi farmers, however, have adopted the principle of this complex and sophisticated technology and made it at a smaller scale, less expensive, and suitable for the nature of his region and its agriculture (Djaber, 2015, p. 129).

The Sufi farmer resorts to pivot irrigation for the following characteristics (Fallah & Bagat, 2020, p. 43):

- ✓ No special care, filtering, or water purification is required;
- ✓ Provides regular water distribution with a continuous slow flow;

- ✓ Operates in desert lands, in harsh conditions, and at temperatures of up to 55 °C;
- ✓ Operates without human intervention.

Pivot irrigation equipment, especially old ones, are affected by climate factors such as wind, which in Oued Souf province reaches up to 50 km/h, causing damage, and leaving it as waste, which causes the environmental landscape of the region to be distorted, as shown in the following pictures

Photo 3: Pivot irrigation equipment waste

Source: Our Field study

3.2 Depletion of agricultural land:

Most farmers in Oued Souf depend on growing potato produce in addition to other crops, as they are more profitable and in high demand. During the 2011/12 agricultural season, potato production was estimated at 1,176,000 quintals, on a total area of about 30,200 hectares, raising it to 35,000 hectares with a total production of 1,153,000 quintals during

the 2016/17 agricultural season. (Directorate of agricultural services, 2018, p. 18). It ranks first nationally in potato production and covers 26% of national consumption, and as a result of this production Algeria has turned from an importing country to an exporting country for this crop (Ahnani, 2020, p. 235).

This agricultural product has negative consequences on the soil, namely the emergence of plant diseases in addition to soil salinization, which affects the yield of the agricultural product. The field study showed that the yield in the early years of land use was 600 quintals per hectare, which started to decrease to about 100-150 quintals per hectare, which lowers the profit return, which could force the farmers to abandon its production.

3.3. Agriculture-based energy

The Oued Souf province Development Projects benefited from a number of agricultural electricity-related operations. During the period 2000-2017, the province benefited from 605 km (Directorate of agricultural services, 2018, p. 12). Only 57% of this has been achieved due to the large size of the projects, and the inability of the National Company for Electricity and Gas to complete this program. (Mostafawi, 2017, pp. 296-297). It has also benefited from connecting and supplying 66 wells with electricity for agricultural wells. (Directorate of agricultural services, 2018, p. 12)

Agricultural farms in the region, based on the field study, relied on various energy sources in the irrigation system, as shown in the following figure:

Fig 3: Energy sources in agriculture

Source: Our Field study

An analysis of the above figure shows that the power used in Oued Souf is 65.83% grid electricity, followed by 19.17% for power generators, As a result of the expansion of agricultural farms and their remoteness from the electrical grid, most farmers are forced to transfer electricity in electrical cables for long distances of up to 2 km, without implementing the safety requirements. Indeed, cable are laid down on the ground, which poses a threat to both farmers and animals. See Photo No. (04).

This method results in frequent power outages and is not sufficient to operate submersible pumps, often causing damage to the latter. Farmers are then forced to change them more than once a year incurring significant operational costs.

Photo 4: The status of the electric cable

Source: Our Field study

The farmers resort to connecting to the electricity grid via cables due to the restrictions imposed on diesel and gasoline sale, considering that the province is a border area where smuggling is active, which forced the authorities to implement limits on the sale of these fuels unless a waiver is granted by the competent authorities. However, due to the remoteness of the farms, which can be more than 10 km away from the power grid, farmers may be forced to generate power using diesel or gasoline. Hence, in addition to the harshness of nature, the farmers have to bear the additional burden of material costs.

Photo 5: Power generator

Source: Our Field study

3.4 How organic materials are used:

The method adopted in fertilizing agricultural land with organic fertilizers may create many environmental problems, because when farmers buy organic materials, they do not use them directly, but rather leave them to dry for up to 15 days. This creates environmental problems, such as bad odors, the spread of harmful insects and diseases.

Photo 6: Organic material used

Source: Our Field study

3.5 Water resources :

Groundwater is the only water source of nutrition in the OuedSouf province, due to the lack of surface streams such as valleys and rivers, and groundwater consists of three layers (Djawadi & Other, 2021-2022, pp. 60-61).

- Surface water layer: Depth of 1-60 m
- Middle water layer: The depth of this layer is 100-400 m
- Deep water layer: The depth of this layer ranges from 1400-1800 m, which is the source of the artesian water.

The surface staining layer (surface water) is the main source of irrigation, which in recent years has seen its levels decrease. According to the field study and the farmers of the area, the area

has experienced a continuous decrease in the level of water in the aquifer (groundwater), by Table (06) we observe that in every 10 years the water level drops by 10 m (1 m) per year, and this percentage may vary from one region to another .

Table 5: Water immersion

Period	1990-2000	2001-2010	2011-2018
a decline in groundwater(m)	8-10	5-10	1-6

Source: Our Field study

4. SOLUTIONS AND PROPOSALS

After reviewing some of the most dynamic environmental problems in the province of Oued Souf, we will attempt to provide some solutions and suggestions to help facilitate the activities of farmers facilitate, on the one hand, and on the other, to ensure environmentally sustainable agriculture and draw the attention of the concerned authorities to these problems with a view to solving them and implementing these proposals and solutions on the ground.

- 1) Create specialized units to treat the remains and waste of the harvest of agricultural produce;
- 2) Educate farmers on the appropriate disposal of wastes generated by burning the produce;
- 3) Ensure that an appropriate agricultural cycle be adopted in order to maintain the continuous exploitation of agricultural land. Some plants such as *Portulaca oleracea* must be introduced to remove the salinization problem in some areas;
- 4) Educate farmers on the importance of analyzing water and soil to reduce the costs of using organic or mineral fertilizers,
- 5) Encourage the use of modern techniques by measuring the amount of water needed by each agricultural product grown at the farm to rationalize the use of water;
- 6) Propose solar energy to farmers as an alternative to electricity, as we have noted that only one farmer in the region uses it, as demonstrated in the field study (see Supplement No. 03);
- 7) Encourage the adoption of modern techniques in the watering of agricultural products, such as smart irrigation and drip irrigation to ensure water conservation;
- 8) Speed up the creation of units to process organic fertilizers and put them into bags for direct use.

5. CONCLUSION

Agricultural dynamism in Oued Souf has led to the expansion of exploited farmland and the diversification and development of agricultural crops, thanks to policies based on agricultural development and reclamation programs that have made it among the most important agricultural poles at the national level. It has taken the lead in potato production, which has evolved in terms of area and production volume. Other field crops such as peanuts, grains and tomatoes have also witnessed a significant development in production. Although the Oued Souf province has achieved dynamism in the field of desert farming, it has been accompanied by many environmental problems such as waste from agricultural farms, depletion of agricultural land, water immersion, and excessive use of pesticides. To ensure environmentally sustainable agriculture and to alert the concerned authorities to these issues, we submitted a number of proposals, the most important of which may be the adoption of modern techniques, such as smart irrigation and distillation irrigation, in irrigating agricultural products. In addition, it is necessary to adopt an agricultural cycle to maintain a sustainable exploitation of agricultural land.

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Appendices

1.

Department	Municipal	Arranged	Surface		Production
			(Ha)	(%)	quintal
Hasssi Khalifa	Hasssi Khalifa	1	6 580	19,9	2173000
Hasssi Khalifa	Trefaoui	3	4 620	14,1	1527000
Total Surface			11200	34,0	3 700 000
Guemar	Guemar	2	5 417	16,4	1 788 216
Ourmas	Taghzout	5	2149	6,5	710 150
Total Surface			7566	22,9	2 498 366
Reguiba	Reguiba	4	4 200	12,7	1 392 000
Total Surface			4 200	12,7	1 392 000
The remaining municipalities (25)		6	10 034	30,4	3 299 634
Total area			10 034	30,4	3 299 634
Total			33 000	100,0	10890000

2.

3.

